

Contribution to the knowledge of longhorn beetles from Dhofar region in sultanate of Oman (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, faunistics, new records, Dhofar, Sultanate of Oman, Palaearctic region.

Abstract: Totally 16 Cerambycidae species are reported for Dhofar in Sultanate of Oman. Ten species are reported for the first time for Oman: *Lygrus longicornis* (Pic, 1895); *Kabatekiella dalihodi* Holzschuh, 2008; *Yementallyrama nasheri* Adlbauer, 2007; *Idactus coquereli* (Fairmaire, 1890); *Apomecyna lameerei* (Pic, 1895); *Enaretta caudata* Fähræus, 1873; *Eunidia breuningae* Villiers, 1951; *Eunidia kristenseni* Aurivillius, 1911; *Eunidia nebulosa nebulosa* Erichson, 1843 and *Coptops aedificator* Fabricius, 1792. The genus *Jordanoleiopus* Lepesme & Breuning, 1955 is new recorder for the fauna of Palaearctic Region.

INTRODUCTION

The cerambycid fauna of Sultanate Oman is very little known, since most of the species hitherto recorded from the Arabian Peninsula, have been collected in Saudi Arabia and Yemen.

The paper presents results of the Czech entomological expedition to Sultanate of Oman in September/October 2011. During this expedition were visited, with a special attention to interesting biotopes in Dhofar region, especially Jabal Samhan and Jabal al Qamar. The expedition included four Czech entomologists, Richard Ambrus, Walter Grosser, Pavel Kučera and Jiří Voříšek.

The beetles were collected individually using generally known methods such as beating, sweeping, individual collecting on wood, flower and leaves. The most effective method for collecting longhorn beetles were used UV light.

The total number of longhorn beetles recorded by Czech expedition from Sultanate of Oman is 16 species, but this is probably only a small number of species actually occurring there.

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All the species of longhorn beetles were determined by Dr. Karl Adlbauer (Graz, Austria), Petr Kabátek (Prague, Czech Republic) and Pierpaolo Rapuzzi (Prepotto, Italy).

Abbreviations:

JV - Jiří Voříšek, Jirkov, CZ

PK - Pavel Kučera, Liberec, CZ

RA - Richard Ambrus, Prague, CZ

WG - Walter Grosser, Opava, CZ

RESULTS

Family CERAMBYCIDAE

Subfamily Prioninae

Tribe Cantharocnemi

1) *Cantharocnemis spondyloides* Audinet-Serville, 1832

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 1 adult attracted by light and remnants of 1 dead adult on ground (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 1 adult attracted by light (WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 1 adult attracted by light (WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 1 adult attracted by light and remnants of 1 dead adult on ground (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km SE Tawi Atayr, 17°3'57.31"N 54°36'17.24"E, 28. 9. 2011, 1 adult attracted by light (PK).

Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Palaearctic Region: North Africa (Egypt, Marocco- Western Sahara), Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

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**Subfamily Cerambycinae
Tribe Cerambycini**

2) *Neoplocaederus denticornis* (Fabricius, 1801)

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°50'41.89"N 53°41'10.14"E, 19. 9. 2011, 4 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 4 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 15 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 12 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, Rakhyut, 16°45'12.53"N 53°23'54.38"E, 23. 9. 2011, 7 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 7 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°51'44.56"N 53°43'18.38"E, 26. 9. 2011, 9 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 33 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, Tawi Atayr env., 17°5'16.94"N 54°37'23.27"E, 1. 10. 2011, 6 adults attracted by light (JV, PK).

Distribution. Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

Tribe Lygrini

3) *Lygrus longicornis* (Pic, 1895)

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 2 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 7 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut,

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16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 2 adults attracted by light (PK, WG).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution. Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

Tribe Oemini

4) *Kabatekiella dalihodi* Holzschuh, 2008

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 8 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 12 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, Rakhyut, 16°45'12.53"N 53°23'54.38"E, 23. 9. 2011, 9 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 68 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, Tawi Atayr env., 17°5'16.94"N 54°37'23.27"E, 1. 10. 2011, 12 adults attracted by light (JV).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution. Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Yemen).

5) *Yementallyrama nasheri* Adlbauer, 2007

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°50'41.89"N 53°41'10.14"E, 19. 9. 2011, 3 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 6 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 29 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 9 adults

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attracted by light (JV, PK); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, Rakhyut, 16°45'12.53"N 53°23'54.38"E, 23. 9. 2011, 4 adults attracted by light (JV, PK); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 6 adults attracted by light (WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 9 adults attracted by light (PK, WG).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution. Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Yemen).

Subfamily Lamiinae
Tribe Acanthocinini

6) *Jordanoleiopus* sp.

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 9 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 3 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 165 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 26 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°51'44.56"N 53°43'18.38"E, 26. 9. 2011, 14 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, Tawi Atayr env., 1. 10. 2011, 17°5'16.94"N 54°37'23.27"E, 5 adults attracted by light (JV, PK).

We were not able to determine this species, but according to Dr. Karl Adlbauer it belongs close to *Jordanoleiopus monoxenus* (Kolbe, 1894) from Afrotropical Region (Tanzania).

The genus *Jordanoleiopus* Lepesme & Breuning, 1955 is new for the fauna of Palaearctic Region.

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Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman).

Tribe Ancytonotini

7) *Idactus coquereli* (Fairmaire, 1890)

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°50'41.89"N 53°41'10.14"E, 19. 9. 2011, 3 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 7 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 9 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 6 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 8 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 7 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, WG).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution: Afrotropical Region, Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Yemen).

8) *Idactus iranicus* Breuning, 1975

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 4 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, WG).

Distribution: Palaearctic Region: Asia (Arab Emirate, Iran, Oman).

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Tribe Apomecynini

9) *Apomecyna lameerei* (Pic, 1895)

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 1 adult attracted by light (JV).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Palaearctic Region: North Africa (Egypt, Morocco), Asia (Arab Emirate, Egypt-Sinai, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Oman, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

10) *Enaretta caudata* Fahraeus, 1873

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 4 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 11 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 4 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°51'44.56"N 53°43'18.38"E, 26. 9. 2011, 3 adults attracted by light (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 5 adults attracted by light (PK, WG).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Palaearctic Region: Asia: Oman, Yemen.

11) *Eunidia breuningae* Villiers, 1951

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°50'41.89"N 53°41'10.14"E, 19. 9. 2011, 5 adults attracted by

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light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 11 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 6 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 5 adults attracted by light (PK, WG).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Palaearctic Region: North Africa (Egypt), Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

12) *Eunidia kristenseni* Aurivillius, 1911

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 1 adult attracted by light (RA).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution: Afrotropical Region, Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

13) *Eunidia nebulosa nebulosa* Erichson, 1843

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°50'41.89"N 53°41'10.14"E, 19. 9. 2011, 3 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 4 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N 53°16'27.26"E, 22. 9. 2011, 7 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km NW Jufa, 17°11'10.14"N 54°56'34.26"E, 27. 9. 2011, 10 adults attracted by light (JV, PK, WG).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

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Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

Tribe Batocerini

14) *Batocera rufomaculata rufomaculata* (DeGeer, 1775)

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 3 adults sitting on *Ficus* sp. (PK, WG); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal Samhan, 15 km SE Tawi Atayr, 28. 9. 2011, 17°3'57.31"N 54°36'17.24"E, 2 adults sitting on *Ficus* sp. (PK).

Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Neotropical Region; Oriental Region; Palaearctic Region:

Asia (Egypt-Sinai, China-Hongkong and Xizang, India-Uttar Pradesh, Israel, Lebanon, Nepal, Oman, Pakistan, Syria, Turkey, Yemen).

Tribe Crossotina

15) *Crossotus arabicus* Gahan, 1896

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N 53°9'12.60"E, 21. 9. 2011, 3 adults reared ex larva from death branches of *Acacia* sp., 1 dead adult was found in a dead branch of *Acacia* sp. and 3 adults attracted by light (PK, RA, WG).

Distribution. Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen).

Tribe Mesosini

16) *Coptops aedificator* Fabricius, 1792

Material. Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N 53°11'40.56"E, 20. 9. 2011, 7 adults attracted by light (PK, RA); Oman, Dhofar, Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N 53°20'13.92"E, 24. 9. 2011, 5 adults attracted by light

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and 2 adults reared ex larva from dead branches and trunks of *Euphorbia* sp. (PK, RA, WG).

This species is new for the fauna of Oman.

Distribution. Afrotropical Region; Oriental Region; Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman, Saudi Arabia, Taiwan, Yemen).

Acknowledgement. We are very grateful to Dr. Karl Adlbauer (Graz, Austria), Petr Kabátek (Prague, Czech Republic) and Pierpaolo Rapuzzi (Prepetto, Italy) for determination and comments on the collected species.

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Получена / Received: 27.03.2012

Принята / Accepted: 30.03.2012